

NOVEL DESIGN OF DUAL CORE RISC ARCHITECTURE IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract- The main goal of the project is simulation and synthesis of the 17bit RISC CPU based on MIPS. RISC is a style or family of processor architecture that share some characteristics and that has been designed to perform a small set of instructions. The most important feature of the RISC processor is that this processor is very simple and support load and store architecture. The design uses Harvard architecture which has distinct program memory space and data memory space. The design consists of four stage pipelining, which involves instruction fetch, instruction decode, execute and write back stage. In this project simulation is done by modelsim to perform logical verification and further synthesizing it on Xilinx-ISE tool using target technology and performing place & routing operation for system verification. The language used here is verilog.

Keywords: MIPS, RISC, Pipelining, Xilinx.

I. INTRODUCTION

RISC or Reduced Instruction Set Computer is a simple architecture that becomes mainstream in the last few years. RISC processor operates on very few data types and does the simple operations. It supports very few addressing modes and is mostly register based. Most of the instructions operate on data present in internal registers. RISC design resulted in computers that execute instructions faster than other computers built of the same technology. In a RISC machine, the instruction set is based upon a load store approach. Only load and store instructions access memory. This is the key to single-cycle execution of instructions. Comparing to CISC, RISC CPU have more advantages, such as faster speed, simplified structure easier implementation. RISC CPU is extensive use in embedded system.

MIPS processor design is based on the RISC design principle that emphasizes on load/store architecture. A major aspect of the MIPS design was to fit every sub-phase, including cache-access, of all instructions into one cycle, thereby removing any needs for interlocking, and permitting a single cycle throughput. MIPS implementations are primarily used in embedded systems such as Windows CE devices, routers, residential gateways,

I. PROPOSED MIPS RISC ARCHITECTURE

Microprocessor without interlocked pipeline stages was abbreviated as MIPS. It was also called as Millions of instructions per second. In conventional approach the MIPS system is designed for the parallel execution. The system consists of several processor modules and dedicated data memory is used for processor operations memory arbiter. This approach uses four clock cycles. Number of gate count increases because individual dedicated memory and an extra arbiter is required. Utilization of chip area is

more, hence the system consumes more power and latency also increases.

To overcome these drawbacks, shared memory architecture is designed. The processors are connected in star topology and share common memory for program and data. Any processor can write/read from the memory at the same time. If collisions occur, they are handled by priority method.

II. PIPELINING

The RISC Processor is designed using pipelined architecture. In this 4-stage pipelining is implemented, with this the speed as well as performance is increased. The four stages of pipeline are fetch, decode, execute and memory read/write back pipelining allows the processor to work on different types of the instruction at the same time, thus more instruction can be executed in a shorter period of time. When the MIPS processor is pipelined during a single clock cycle each one of those modules or stage is in use at exactly the same time executing on different instruction in parallel. The basic architecture of RISC pipelined processor is shown in the below figure 1.

Fig 1. Basic architecture of RISC Pipelined processor

At any given time there are 4 instructions in different stages of execution

Fig 2. Instruction execution using Pipelining technique

The figure 2. shows how instructions are executed using the pipelining technique.

The 4 stages of pipelining are

Instruction Fetch (IF):

The Instruction Fetch stage is where a program counter (8 bit) will pull the next instruction from the correct location in program memory. Obtain next instruction from memory. Loads the instruction into instruction register IR and the MAR is loaded with instruction pointer. Here the instruction is loaded through the MDR. Once the instruction is fetched the program counter will be incremented and it updates instruction pointer address while reading instruction from memory.

Instruction Decode (ID):

The Instruction Decode stage examines op code of the instruction. Depending on the opcode it will determine which operation to perform . Output line signals a circuit which implements the corresponding operation.

Execute Unit (EX):

The Execute stage is where the instruction is actually sent to the ALU and executed. If necessary, branch locations are calculated in this stage as well. Initially it computes the address of the memory location of the instruction operand, and then Loads MAR with address calculated. later Reads memory into MDR, making data available as input to the processing unit. The Microcode for the instruction, selected by the decoder output line, is executed by the ALU.

Store result (ST):

If the instruction is a load, memory does a read using the effective address computed in the previous cycle that can be stored. Instruction Cycle begins anew.

III. RISC & CISC COMPARISON

Processors have traditionally been designed around two Philosophies: Complex Instruction Set

Computer (CISC) and Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC). The comparison between RISC and CISC architecture is shown below.

RISC	CISC
Multiple register set	Single register set
Less addressing mode	More addressing mode
Few instruction	Many instruction
Fixed format instruction	Variable format instruction
No microcode	Micro code used
Highly pipelined	Non pipelined
Only load/store reference memory	Any instruction many reference memory
Simple instruction taking one cycle	Complex instruction taking multiple cycle
Realization is easy	Realization is difficult
Faster	slower

IV. RISC SPECIFICATIONS

- Architecture contains 23 instructions (6 arithmetic+8 logical+4 datapath+5 branching instruction)
- Four stage instruction execution (IF, ID, IE, ST).
- Harvard memory architecture.
- 8Bit data and 8bit address bus.
- 8 Bit memory mapped I/O register.
- 1 Special purpose status register.
- 13 General purpose CPU registers uniform instruction width for all the instruction.

V. INSTRUCTION SET

ISA(Instruction Set Architecture) of processor is composed of instruction set and corresponding registers. Program based on same ISA can run on the same instruction set. The instruction set used in this architecture consists of arithmetic instructions, logical instructions, branch instructions and memory instructions.

The different addressing modes in an instruction set architecture define how machine language instructions in that architecture identify the operand (or operands) of each instruction. The addressing mode used in proposed method is: Register addressing mode.

17 bit address with opcode of 5bit and three operands each of 4 bits. The data width, status register, program counter are of 8 bit. 23 instructions are used in this processor and taken in ROM memory of this processor. The instruction format is of register type

and is shown in Figure 3. Instruction of 17 bit with opcode 5bit and three operands of each 4 bit.

Fig 3. Instruction set of RISC processor

ALU Instructions:

Arithmetic operations either take two registers as operands or take one register and a immediate value as an operand. Some arithmetic instructions are ADD, SUB, MUL, DIV, INC and DEC. The result is stored in a third register. Logical operations such as AND OR, XOR, NOT, Shift left, Shift right with carry, Shift left with carry. Shift right are used.

Data path operations:

Usually take a register (base register) as an operand and a immediate value. The sum of the two will create the effective address. A second register acts as a source in the case of a load operation. In the case of a store operation the second register contains the data to be stored. Examples are: LW, SW etc. Move immediate (MVI), Register moving (MOV) are also used as data path operations.

Branch instructions:

A branch causes an immediate value to be added to the current program counter. Some common branch instructions are BZ (Branch Zero), BNZ (Branch if not Zero), BC(Branch carry),BNC(Branch if no carry) and GOTO (goto specified address).

VI. FLOW CHART

There are four stages to execute any instruction in the MIPS RISC implementation that is shown in the flow chart given below. The process starts when PC value sent to the instruction memory which contains the code, after that the PC will be incremented. Later the instruction is fetched and determines whether the fetched instruction has to read on the register or to register from the memory.

Later instructions are decoded and instruction function is sent to the ALU unit, where all calculations are performed and produce the result. This result is given as input to the data memory. Data memory is used for load and stores the values to and from the memory. Depending on the instruction it performs the read or write operation.

Fig 4. Steps in RISC implementation

VII. SIMULATION RESULTS

The single core RISC processor or CPU is simulated by using pipeline concept and Xilinx ISE and Modelsim simulator is used to get results. The Verilog HDL language is used for designing the CPU. The top level design of CPU processor for single core RISC processor obtained in Xilinx ISE is shown in Figure5. The RTL schematic for single

RISC processor obtained in Xilinx is shown in Figure6.

Fig 5. Top level design of RISC processor.

Fig 6. RTL Schematic of RISC processor.

The simulation waveform for Single core CPU is obtained by using Modelsim is shown in Figure7. Here there is a five input such as clock (1bit), reset (1bit), input1 (4 bit), input2 (4 bit), ram data (4 bit). The data read from ram by using load instruction. The output are op (4 bit), ram write (8 bit).

Fig7: Simulation waveform for single RISC processor.

The design summary shows device utilization out of available devices. The utilization of registers, flip-flops, latches etc. are shown in terms of percentage.

Logic Utilization	Used	Available	Utilization
Total Number Slice Registers	152	9,312	1%
Number used as Flip Flops	148		
Number used as Latches	4		
Number of 4 input LUTs	581	9,312	6%
Number of occupied Slices	300	4,656	6%
Number of Slices containing only related logic	300	300	100%
Number of Slices containing unrelated logic	0	300	0%
Total Number of 4 input LUTs	581	9,312	6%
Number of bonded IOBs	51	232	21%
Number of RAMB16s	1	20	5%
Number of BUFPGMUXs	1	24	4%
Number of MULT18X18SIOs	1	20	5%

Fig 8: Design summary of CPU.

CONCLUSION

17 bit instruction set RISC Processor core has been design and simulated in Xilinx ISE 14.1. The design has been achieved using Verilog and simulated with Modelsim simulator. After synthesis got the less no of logic resource utilization comparing the available resources this can be show in the device utilization summary table.

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